

TASK-BASED LEARNING MODULE IN MATHEMATICS IN IMPROVING THE COMPUTATIONAL SKILLS OF GRADE V STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics is perceived as one of the challenging subjects for students, and upon assessments, the problem lies within the learners' computational skills. As a response, this study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Task-based Learning Module in Mathematics in Improving the Computational Skills of Grade V Students. The study used descriptive-experimental research design in conducting the study and focused on describing the structure of the lesson, respondents' evaluation of the module, and determining the effectiveness of using the task-based learning module in improving the computational skills of the 35 Grade V students of Rosendo Algenio Elementary School of the School Year 2020-2021. The study utilized survey questionnaires, pre-test, and posttest as instruments. The result of the study revealed that the respondents described the structure of the module in terms of pre-task, task, and review as very well structured. Likewise, the findings show that the respondents described the evaluation of the module in terms of adaptability, clarity, validity, usability, and aesthetic value to a very great extent. Further, the result showed a significant difference and improvement in the mastery level of the students in computational skills in terms of problem-solving, decision making, sequencing, algorithm formation, and quantitative measurement. Furthermore, no significant relationship was found between the described structure of the lesson and the level of mastery of the students in computational skills. Moreover, the findings also revealed that there is no significant relationship between the described evaluation of the module and the computational skills of the students. Thus, this study recommends the use of a task-based learning module in Mathematics to improve the computational skills of the students.

Keywords: Task-based Learning Module, Computational Skills